

Dating and placing Visigothic script codices: A quick guide for beginners

1. Introduction

Looking at a medieval manuscript, regardless of what our eye is expecting to find, our mind instantly opens to a period in which handwriting was much more than a means to an end that allowed people to communicate. The script, the ideas put into writing, were respected for their legal meaning when building charters and cartularies, and for their spiritual connection as tangible representations of the sacred word when composing ecclesiastical or liturgical codices. Something that was important enough to be written deserved from the people who wrote, copied, read and saw manuscripts a deep respect that is difficult for us to imagine today, our modern eyes being more familiar with writing and reading in digital format. With the purpose of digging into that atmosphere of medieval handwritten culture, historians approach material sources with an open mind, reading and interpreting the texts preserved, while specialists of manuscript studies try to reveal how these manuscript were created, their history. Nowadays the questions with which we interrogate a medieval manuscript might not have changed, but our way of 'looking' at a source to answer them has, our options are enriched.

A digital surrogate of a medieval manuscript offers endless options to alter an image to confirm or refute a theory. To palaeographers, it provides the opportunity to keep a sample of the script to which one can come back later, maybe to look again with a different question, from a different angle, or with more experienced eyes. All the efforts of specialists working on manuscripts aim to better understand medieval text; to learn more about the people who read, wrote and copied that text; who were they, when the manuscript was made, in which cultural context, and to what purpose. Most of the time, particularly when working with charters or cartularies, there are clues directly embedded in the text to help answer these questions. When the primary source is a codex, though, colophons are rather infrequent or unreliable, thus leaving many of these queries unanswered. Textual research can reconstruct the life of the text contained in a codex, how it spread through *scriptoria* over the centuries. Codicological analysis can provide equally significant information about the tradition in which the archaeology of the codex fits. Palaeography can deconstruct the strokes that make each letter to provide a place and a date for a manuscript to start to build an idea of its context. Medieval history provides the methodology with which to encompass all this information, closing a circle of interdisciplinary collaboration.

Through years of palaeographic analysis, scholars have identified unique features that allow the cultural contextualisation of each medieval script: specific features or graphic characteristics which point towards a defined historical period and to a particular place. This essay re-examines the most significant graphic evidence that has been discussed to help date and place codices written or copied in Visigothic minuscule script, the characteristic hand of the medieval Iberian Peninsula; it will also briefly refer to the new digital methods that could help, in the near future, to better test and reconsider this evidence.

2. On sounds, feet and ascenders

Scholars analysing the peculiarities of the Visigothic minuscule script hands in which almost four hundred surviving codices are written – ranging from ecclesiastical texts to books on law and glossaries¹ – have observed some recurring features that seem to relate to a specific

¹ A. Millares Carlo, *Corpus de códices visigóticos*, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria: Gobierno de Canarias; Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia, Centro Asociado de Las Palmas, 1999. For an online version as summary of this work, see A. Castro Correa, "Online Catalogue of Visigothic script codices," *Littera*

chronological stage of the script's development. Bearing in mind that early medieval scripts do not tend to show an invariable graphic model in the same way as late medieval scripts and scribes do, these aspects are not conclusive evidence. They do, however, indicate a given period for a determined manuscript's hand: a starting point from which to start reconstructing its likely cultural context.

Figures 1 and 2 reproduce a graphic example of the basic characteristics of a single representative Visigothic minuscule script hand, the typological variant most often used in codices.² This hand corresponds to a highly skilled scribe writing in an elegant calligraphic script in the last decade of the eleventh century in a Benedictine monastery in northern Iberian Peninsula. This scribe, the first to work on the 'Silos Apocalypse', can be easily placed in space and time thanks to the multiple colophons included in the codex. The scribe's context and that of the book can thus be reconstructed. If the manuscript did not provide this information, the detailed analysis of the graphic characteristics of the scribe's hand would provide significant evidence in this direction, traditionally relying on the features discussed below.

The features are grouped in two categories, linguistic and stylistic. The first is represented here by the two different sounds the syllable *ti* can have in medieval Latin – how each scribe wrote that syllable; the example of a stylistic feature, the way in which a scribe drawn the feet or last stroke of the letters *m*, *n* and *h*, and the style in which they mannered the ascenders (the vertical strokes of letters like *b* or *d*) of the tall letters.

2.1. Linguistic features: The syllable *ti*

The syllable *ti* has two different sounds in Latin: sibilated/soft and assibilated/hard. In the first case, the sound *ti* is represented either by *ci* or by a ligature formed between the letters *t* and *i* longa (a letter which resembles a modern *j*; see the example in Figure 2, left column, line 4, second ligature). In the second case, the sound *ti* is represented simply by writing the letters *t* and *i* in their regular form (see Figure 2, minuscule alphabet). A more or less chronological consistency on how a Visigothic script scribe represented these two sounds throughout the centuries was first spotted by E. A. Lowe.³

By analysing the examples of dated manuscripts published by Delisle,⁴ Muñoz y Rivero⁵ and Loewe and Eward⁶ among others, and based on this *ti/tj* criterion, Lowe proposed a distinction in the representation of the two different sounds of *tii* by Visigothic script scribes, differentiating three stages. According to Lowe, from the eighth century to the first half of the ninth, there was no distinction of *ti* and *tj*; from the middle of the ninth century to the first decades of the tenth, it started to be progressively clear in some hands (some scribes used it, others did not), whereas

Visigothica (2013-2015). Last visited on 5 December 2019: <http://www.litteravisigothica.com/visigothic-script-topics/codicology>.

² There is only one extant example of Visigothic cursive script (*elongata* variant) used in codices: the *Liber Testamentorum Ovetensis* (dated 1118). See E. E. Rodríguez Díaz, M^a J. Sanz Fuentes, J. Yarza Luaces and E. Fernández Vallina, *Liber Testamentorum Ecclesiae Ovetensis*, 2 vols., Barcelona: M. Moleiro Editor, 1995.

³ E. A. Lowe, *Studia Palaeographica. A contribution to the history of early Latin minuscule and to the dating of Visigothic MSS*, München: Verlag des Kgl. Bayerischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, 1910, pp. 52-54, 78-80.

⁴ L. V. Delisle, *Mélanges de paléographie et de bibliographie*, Paris: Champion libraire, 1880.

⁵ J. Muñoz y Rivero, *Paleografía visigoda. Método teórico-práctico para aprender a leer los códices y documentos españoles de los siglos V al XIII*, Madrid: Daniel Jorro editor, 1919 (2^a ed.; 1^a ed. 1881).

⁶ G. Loewe and H. P. Ewald, *Exempla scripturae visigoticae XL tabulis expressa : liberalitate ministerii quod regni borvssici rebvs ecclesiasticis scholasticis medicinalibvs praeest abivti edidervnt Pavlvus Ewald et Gvstavvs Loewe ; tabulas photographicas arte Antonii Selfa Escorialensis maximam partem confectas phototypice descripservnt A. Navmann & Schroeder Lipsienses*, Heidelberg: apvd Gvstavvm Koester, 1883.

from the second half of the tenth century to the twelfth, the differentiation of the two sounds represented by *ti* seemed always to have been respected by scribes.

The validity of this periodisation has been tested by many scholars since Lowe, the first being Millares Carlo. In the first edition of his *Tratado de Paleografía*, the major manual of Spanish palaeography published to date, Millares stated his agreement with this periodisation, considering it of "the highest importance".⁷ He remarked, however, that his own research showed that in none of the known codices dated as copied in the ninth century were the two sounds of *ti* distinguished, and that the transitional period was consequently limited to the first half of the tenth century.⁸ Based on how a hand represented the sound *ti* in a given Visigothic minuscule script codex, then, it could be placed in the eighth or ninth century if there is no distinction (the scribe employed either *ti* or *ci*), in the early tenth if it is marked now and then, and in the mid-tenth, eleventh, or twelfth century if the scribe consistently differentiated between the two sounds (*ti* and *tj*).

García Larragueta⁹ revised Lowe's rule more recently, reducing the periodisation to two stages. He observed that the distinction between *ti* and *tj* was only occasional in those codices dated by current scholarship as copied in the eighth and ninth centuries, while in those attributed to the late tenth century onwards, the distinction was generalised. García based his assessment of Lowe's rule on Mundó i Marcet's work on the problem of dating and placing Visigothic script codices,¹⁰ thoroughly reassessing the liturgical codices in Visigothic script supposedly copied in Toledo. Although the differentiation of *ti/tj* seemed to be characteristic enough in Visigothic script manuscript production as to be taken under thoughtful consideration, the rule their use appears to follow was, for both scholars, another unusual feature and not the only one to help better contextualise sources. The characteristic graphic archaism shown by the Toletan codices revealed that the *ti/tj* distinction must be considered neither indisputable nor in isolation since it strongly depends on the scribe's cultural environment.¹¹

Inspired by the debate on the forms of *ti/tj* and the importance of examining each manuscript in its full complexity and in accordance with its context, in more recent years scholars such as Ruiz Albi¹² have come back to the topic, expanding it further to consider not only codices written in Visigothic script but also charters. Ruiz questioned whether, for example, the eleventh-century scribes who copied an exemplar written in Visigothic script and dated in the ninth or tenth century, maintained the non-differentiation that should have characterised their archetype – in other words, whether the distinction had a specific chronology or not. In many cases, scribes who copied codices were also commissioned to write charters, and thus the differentiation of sibilated or assibilated *ti* should also be present in this other type of manuscript source. Ruiz therefore considered the corpus of charters in Visigothic script held by the Cathedral of Leon, dividing their

⁷ A. Millares Carlo, *Tratado de Paleografía Española*, 3 vols., Madrid: Editorial Espasa-Calpe, 1983 (2^a ed., con la colaboración de J. M. Ruiz Asencio), vol. I, p. 127.

⁸ A. Millares Carlo, *Tratado de Paleografía Española*, 3 vols., Madrid: Editorial Espasa-Calpe, 1983 (2^a ed., con la colaboración de J. M. Ruiz Asencio), vol. I, pp. 129-130.

⁹ S. A. García Larragueta, "Consideraciones sobre la datación de códices en escritura visigótica," in M. C. Díaz y Díaz (coord.), *Actas del VIII Coloquio del Comité Internacional de Paleografía Latina (Madrid-Toledo, 29 septiembre-1 octubre 1987)*, Madrid: Joyas Bibliográficas (Serie Estudios y Ensayos 16), 1990, pp. 51-58.

¹⁰ A. M. Mundó i Marcet, "La datación de los códices litúrgicos visigóticos toledanos", in *Hispania Sacra* XVIII/35, 1965, pp. 1-25.

¹¹ As, on the other hand, had already been observed by E. A. Lowe, *Studia Palaeographica. A contribution to the history of early Latin minuscule and to the dating of Visigothic MSS*, München: Verlag des Kgl. Bayerischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, 1910, p. 78.

¹² I. Ruiz Albi, "La distinción gráfica *ti/tj* en los documentos visigóticos del archivo de la Catedral de León", in *Orígenes de las lenguas romances en el reino de León. Siglos IX-XII*, 2 vols.. León: Centro de Estudios e Investigación "San Isidoro" (Colección de Fuentes y Estudios de Historia Leonesa, 103), 2004, pp. 439-456.

analysis by typological variants of the script – thus including hands in Visigothic cursive script. Her study reached consistent conclusions: in those charters written in Visigothic cursive, the distinction predominates from the early years of the tenth century; hands using the semi-cursive variant (a mix between the cursive and the minuscule that still needs to be thoroughly studied) show distinction from the mid-tenth century; whereas charters written or copied in Visigothic minuscule distinguished *ti/tj* from the last quarter of the tenth century on. Ruiz also found isolated examples of no distinction in all three typological variants of Visigothic script in the twelfth century.¹³

Considering the conclusions and remarks of scholars and given the sources preserved, it therefore can be said that during the eighth and ninth centuries the form *tj* was only rarely used to indicate the sibilated sound of *ti* in Visigothic script manuscripts; in the next century its use seems to have grown progressively (particularly in codices), although there were scribes who did not distinguish the two sounds, while in the eleventh century the *ti/tj* distinction spread, only to decrease again in the twelfth century. Lowe's rule can, therefore, suggest a specific period but not categorically.

An aspect that still needs attention is the explanation that justifies why this spoken distinction became graphically evident. It could be argued whether the improvement of the educational system, particularly in relation to the knowledge of Latin promoted in the peninsula in relation to the Gregorian reform, could be worthy of being taken into account.¹⁴ Further intensification of writing for practical purposes, and increase in the number of scribes with different levels of training, could also justify the decrease in the graphic differentiation of the two sounds of *ti* noted in the twelfth century. A similar theory could be applied to the graphic representation of the two sounds of the letter *d*, occlusive in initial position and in contact with other consonants and approximate in intervocalic and final position, represented within the Visigothic script's graphic model in two allographs: a minuscule form used at the beginning of a word and an uncial form mostly used at the end or in the middle when in-between vowels (see Figure 2).¹⁵ Either way, both notes are merely hypotheses that require a detailed and interdisciplinary study; it would be extremely useful to incorporate a linguistic study into this palaeographic discussion to better understand how the *ti/tj* and *d* differentiations were perceived by the scribes as a written representation of a practical everyday spoken use.

2.2. Stylistic features: The letters *m*, *n* and *h* and the ascenders

To assess his *ti*-distinction rule more accurately, Lowe also noted¹⁶ two other aspects which seemed to correspond to a specific historical period in the development of Visigothic script:

¹³ The same results have been obtained by analysing the extant charters in Visigothic script from the diocese of Lugo (Galicia). See A. Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica en Galicia. I. Diócesis de Lugo" (PhD diss.), Bellaterra: Servei de Publicacions de la Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 2012, p. 324.

¹⁴ A. Castro Correa, "Visigothic script vs. Caroline minuscule: the collision of two cultural worlds in twelfth-century Galicia", in *Mediaeval Studies*, 78, 2016, pp. 203-242.

¹⁵ On the topic see A. Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica en Galicia. I. Diócesis de Lugo" (PhD diss.), Bellaterra: Servei de Publicacions de la Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 2012, pp. 248-249, 405, 539, 627, 682, and D. Stutzmann, "Paléographie statistique pour décrire, identifier, dater... Normaliser pour coopérer et aller plus loin?", in F. Fischer, C. Fritze and G. Vogeler (eds.), *Codicology and Palaeography in the Digital Age 2*, Norderstedt: BoD, 2010, pp. 247-277 (255-256, note 13).

¹⁶ E. A. Lowe, *Studia Palaeographica. A contribution to the history of early Latin minuscule and to the dating of Visigothic MSS*, München: Verlag des Kgl. Bayerischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, 1910, pp. 80-81.

the form of the feet and ascenders of the letters. He was relying on studies on Visigothic script published, particularly, in Muñoz y Rivero's *Paleografía visigoda*.¹⁷

Lowe analysed the way in which a given Visigothic minuscule hand finished the letters *h*, *m* and *n*. Mostly relying on dated manuscript examples, he observed that when the last stroke of these letters turned backwards or ended on the baseline, the hand tended to correspond to the oldest examples (eighth and ninth centuries), whereas when the stroke turned out or continued on the baseline with a serif, it usually corresponded to a more modern hand (late ninth/early tenth century or mid-tenth/mid-eleventh century, respectively). Lowe also noted that the arches of the letters *h*, *m* and *n* were lower in the earlier examples, while the script was taller and narrower in the latter period.

Lowe also focused on the weight of the pen stroke, particularly when drawing the ascenders of tall letters such as *b*, minuscule *d*, *h*, or *l*. He observed that in those manuscripts dated to the eighth and ninth centuries, the script was more compact, with a thick ("not fine") pen stroke; in those from the late ninth and early tenth centuries, the ascenders were club-shaped; and in codices from the mid-tenth or eleventh centuries, the pen stroke was "often fine". Going further, Lowe also recognised that those Visigothic minuscule sources dated to the twelfth century belonged to a period of decline in which exogenous graphic influence was patent (see below).

Millares Carlo dismissed both criteria – the form of the last stroke of *h*, *m* and *n*, and that of the ascenders – as "too absolute".¹⁸ As with the *ti*-distinction rule, neither can be judged conclusively. However, they provide clues to the chronological stage of the evolution of Visigothic minuscule script that should be taken into consideration.

Figure 3 presents three representative examples of minuscule hands. At the top is a sample from a codex – a *Liber Iudicum* – that is supposed to have been copied in or near the monastery of San Millán de la Cogolla (La Rioja).¹⁹ The hand represented in the fragment shows no distinction between the two sounds of *ti* (*licentiam* l.3); the last stroke of *h*, *m* and *n* ends on the baseline, with a short serif in some cases; and the pen stroke is very thick. According to Lowe's revised rules, this hand should correspond to the ninth or beginning of the tenth century. The codex is dated by current scholarship as a ninth-century example. The middle example is from a folio of the Beatus of Tábara, copied in the monastery of San Salvador de Tábara (Zamora).²⁰ The hand shows the distinction of *ti/tj* (*pēnitentjam* l.1), the letters *h*, *m* and *n* end in a serif over the baseline, and the pen stroke is lighter than in the previous example. By Lowe's rules, this codex should be dated to the tenth or eleventh century, and indeed the manuscript has a colophon which dates the completion of the codex to 970. At the bottom, the third example is part of the opening

¹⁷ J. Muñoz y Rivero, *Paleografía visigoda. Método teórico-práctico para aprender a leer los códices y documentos españoles de los siglos V al XIII*, Madrid: Daniel Jorro editor, 1919 (2^a ed.; 1^a ed. 1881), p. 29, discusses how the general aspect of the script changes around the tenth century, becoming progressively more regular and open to exogenous influence. On the chronological evolution of Visigothic script, see below.

¹⁸ A. Millares Carlo, "De paleografía visigótica. A propósito del *Codex Toletanus*", in *Revista de Filología Española*, 12, 1925, pp. 252-270 (255) and A. Millares Carlo, *Tratado de Paleografía Española*, 3 vols., Madrid: Editorial Espasa-Calpe, 1983 (2^a ed., con la colaboración de J. M. Ruiz Asencio), vol. I., p. 127.

¹⁹ On this manuscript see A. Millares Carlo, *Corpus de códices visigóticos*, 2 vols., Las Palmas de Gran Canaria: Gobierno de Canarias; Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia, Centro Asociado de Las Palmas, 1999, vol. I, p. 131, n^o 193.

Available at <http://bibliotecadigital.rah.es/dgbrah/es/consulta/registro.cmd?id=41>.

²⁰ On this manuscript, see A. Millares Carlo, *Corpus de códices visigóticos*, 2 vols., Las Palmas de Gran Canaria: Gobierno de Canarias; Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia, Centro Asociado de Las Palmas, 1999, pp. 92-94, n^o 128; M. C. Díaz y Díaz, *Códices visigóticos en la monarquía leonesa*, León: Centro de Estudios e Investigación "San Isidoro" (C.S.I.C.), 1983, pp. 318-321.

Available at <http://pares.mcu.es>.

page of the Silos Apocalypse, copied in the monastery of Santo Domingo de Silos (Burgos).²¹ It shows distinction of *ti/tj* (*dilectjonis* l.1); the letters *h*, *m* and *n* end in a serif over the baseline, which is more developed than in the previous example; and the pen stroke is thin, with a distinctive approach stroke in the ascenders. Following Lowe's rules, it should be from the eleventh or twelfth century and indeed its colophon describes the text as completed in 1091 (the illumination was completed in 1109).

1) Differentiation of the two sounds of the syllable <i>ti</i> (' <i>ti</i> ' represented as ' <i>ti</i> ' vs ' <i>ci</i> ' represented as ' <i>tj</i> ')	
8 th -9 th c.	none or seldom distinction
10 th c.	progressive differentiation <i>ti/tj</i>
11 th c.	differentiation <i>ti/tj</i>
12 th c.	decrease of differentiation <i>ti/tj</i>
2) Form of the serifs of letters like <i>h</i> , <i>m</i> , or <i>n</i>	
8 th -9 th c.	the last stroke turns to the left or stays on the baseline
10 th c.	the last stroke develops on the baseline or to the right
11 th -12 th c.	the last stroke develops to the right
3) Form of the ascenders (thicker = older)	
8 th -9 th c.	thick stroke
10 th c.	clubbed
11 th -12 th c.	thin stroke

Table 1. Lowe's rules (1910, *Studia Palaeographica*) [updated]

As can be seen from the analysis of these examples, particularly the last two, Lowe's rules (Table 1) can prove useful. However, this is so only because these manuscripts were copied in the northern Iberian Peninsula, more precisely in Castile and Leon, in three of the most renowned monasteries of their time. They are thus products of similar cultural contexts.

All the scholars who have revised Lowe's rules have emphasised their simplicity and usefulness while stressing the need to consider the cultural context of the text, and its tendency to modern or more traditional graphic forms. Therefore, although some aspects of Lowe's criteria could be correct for a determined source, to accurately date and locate Visigothic minuscule script hands it is necessary to adopt more perspectives of palaeographical analysis in combination with the consideration of each hand's historical context, namely, the classification of the script by geographical variants and the study of how the script's graphic evolution fits each.

3. On geographical, regional and local variants, and on the life of Visigothic script

Another set of intertwined criteria has been established to help date and place manuscripts produced in Visigothic minuscule script. They are based on the notion of Visigothic script as a malleable cultural representation of a specific context which was adapted by the people

²¹ On this manuscript, see A. Millares Carlo, *Corpus de códices visigóticos*, 2 vols., Las Palmas de Gran Canaria: Gobierno de Canarias; Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia, Centro Asociado de Las Palmas, 1999, pp. 81-84, n^o 106; M. C. Díaz y Díaz, *Códices visigóticos en la monarquía leonesa*, León: Centro de Estudios e Investigación "San Isidoro" (C.S.I.C.), 1983, pp. 312-313, 399-400; A. Castro Correa, "The scribes of the Silos Apocalypse (British Library Add. ms. 11695) and the *scriptorium* of Silos in the late eleventh century", in *Speculum*, 95/2, 2020 (in press). Available at http://www.bl.uk/manuscripts/FullDisplay.aspx?ref=Add_MS_11695.

who wrote and read the manuscripts, and thus mirroring in its basic graphic model the historical, political, social and economical developments in their environment. In a way, Lowe's rules indirectly included this perspective. Still, it could be said that the undue attention to particular features obscured the broader consideration of the script as part of a whole. Lowe observed how specific traits were picked up by Visigothic script scribes from the manuscripts they copied, but failed to see how these scribes were integrated into the larger community of peninsular production centres and how this manuscript culture changed throughout the Middle Ages and across Iberia. These new criteria, more than particular features, are based on how Visigothic script was adopted, adapted and developed in each of the areas of the Iberian Peninsula and Septimania in which it was used.

During the lifespan of Visigothic script, from the sixth century, when some letters and ligatures of what would become the Visigothic script's alphabet were already being employed,²² to far into the thirteenth century, when the last extant codex was copied in Visigothic script,²³ the script was adapted and evolved in different ways depending on the geographical area. Since realising this, scholars have been paying particular attention to the graphic differences observed and their chronology in order to correctly group manuscripts by periods of evolution and by geographical areas, by regions, or by main production centres.

3.1. The people and their script

Although there was no variation in the thematic of the texts copied,²⁴ Visigothic script varied across the Iberian Peninsula. Each area had, and still has, cultural peculiarities that were reflected in the script.

The first three geographical variants, or graphic schools, of Visigothic minuscule script to be distinguished by scholars by their graphic characteristics were the traditionally called Mozarabic referring to the script used by the Christian arabised communities of southern Iberia,²⁵ the Astur-Leonese,²⁶ and soon after the Portuguese.²⁷ The recovery of more sources and more detailed study of their morphological and brachygraphic (abbreviation system) characteristics then led to

²² A. M. Mundó i Marçet, "Notas para la historia de la escritura visigótica en su período primitivo," in *Bivium: Homenaje a Manuel Cecilio Díaz y Díaz*, Madrid: Gredos, 1983, pp. 175-196 (178-179).

²³ Madrid, Biblioteca Nacional, mss 10110. On this manuscript, see A. Millares Carlo, *Corpus de códices visigóticos*, 2 vols., Las Palmas de Gran Canaria: Gobierno de Canarias; Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia, Centro Asociado de Las Palmas, 1999, pp. 121-122, n^o 173.

²⁴ See A. Castro Correa, "Online Catalogue of Visigothic script codices," *Littera Visigothica* (2013-2015) (last visited on 5 December 2019: <http://www.litteravisigothica.com/visigothic-script-topics/codicology>) with a spreadsheet listing the content of each codex, its date and origin.

²⁵ The references that follow correspond to the most recent and significant publications. On the differentiation of Visigothic script by regional variants, see J. Alturo Perucho, "La escritura visigótica de origen transpirenaico. Una aproximación a sus particularidades", in *Hispania Sacra*, XLVI/93, 1994, pp. 33-64. For a full list of main bibliographic references on "Mozarabic" Visigothic script, see M^a del C. del Camino Martínez, "La escritura visigótica de los centros mozárabes en su período primitivo", in J. Alturo Perucho, M. Torras Cortina and A. Castro Correa (coords. and eds.), *La escritura visigótica en la Península Ibérica: nuevas aportaciones*, Bellaterra: Servei de Publicacions de la Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 2012, pp. 115-143. Note the duality between Mozarabic centres, in which Mozarabic Visigothic script codices were produced, and Mozarabic scribes, who travelled across the peninsula carrying with them their characteristic script.

²⁶ On Astur-leonese Visigothic script, see A. Millares Carlo, *Tratado de Paleografía Española*, 3 vols., Madrid: Editorial Espasa-Calpe, 1983 (2^a ed., con la colaboración de J. M. Ruiz Asencio), vol. I, caps. ix, x, xi.

²⁷ M^a J. Azevedo Santos, *Da visigótica à carolina. A escrita em Portugal de 882 a 1172*, Lisboa: Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian, 1994.

the differentiation of two further geographical variants, the Pyrenaic or Catalan²⁸ and the Septimanian or southern French.²⁹

Comparing variants (see Figure 4), the Mozarabic Visigothic minuscule script differs from the Astur-Leonese, for example, in some distinctive letters: the Mozarabic scribes seem to have preferred the use of open (over closed) *e*, not only in ligatures, as is common to the other variants, but also in isolated position; the *ductus* of the letter *t* is consistently different, adopting an infinity-like form in the Mozarabic. Again, comparing geographical areas, while the Astur-Leonese script is more consistent with the standard model, the Septimanian and Catalan variants are more open to European graphic systems as a consequence of their regions' close geographical and political connections with the Carolingian Empire,³⁰ showing an early incorporation of letters, ligatures and abbreviations of the coeval Caroline minuscule.³¹

Broadly speaking, the dissimilarities between geographical variants or main graphic schools are significant enough to justify their differentiation, it being relatively unproblematic to link a specific source to a specific variant. However, within these broad groups remain vast cultural differences – pro-European centres open to external graphic and cultural influence versus traditional, inward-looking ones – that complicate the attribution of a geographical context to a graphic example. The cultural context was not the same in all areas of the Mozarabic Peninsula, the Astur-Leonese north, or the eastern regions. In consequence, after careful consideration of the sources preserved, within the Catalan geographical variant, it was individualised as a regional variant the Aragonese,³² and the Riojan,³³ Castilian, Leonese,³⁴ and Galician within the Astur-Leonese.³⁵ Also, the Visigothic script used in Toledo and nearby centres displays a constant

²⁸ J. Alturo Perucho, "Manuscrits i documents llatins d'origen català del segle IX", in *Symposium Internacional sobre els orígens de Catalunya (segles VIII-XI)*, 2 vols., Barcelona: Reial Acadèmia de Bones Lletres (Memorias de la RABLB), 1991, vol. I, pp. 273-280.

²⁹ J. Alturo Perucho, "La escritura visigótica de origen transpirenaico. Una aproximación a sus particularidades", in *Hispania Sacra*, XLVI/93, 1994, pp. 33-64.

³⁰ This European cultural and graphic influence would spread down the Way of St James from east to west, strengthened by political and ecclesiastic factors (on this topic, see A. Castro Correa, "Visigothic script vs. Caroline minuscule: the collision of two cultural worlds in twelfth-century Galicia", in *Mediaeval Studies*, 78, 2016, pp. 203-242 and A. Castro Correa, "Leaving the past behind, adapting to the future: transitional and polygraphic Visigothic-Caroline minuscule scribes", in *CSIC Anuario de Estudios Medievales*, 50/1, 2020 (in press).

³¹ There is as yet no monograph in which all the geographical variants are thoroughly compared. Such a study could potentially lead to the assimilation of variants that are currently thought to be different or to the differentiation of further graphic schools. In order to appreciate the differences among them, it is recommended to revise at least the main references listed in the footnotes corresponding to this and the following paragraphs.

³² Á. Canellas López, "Paleografía aragonesa de la Alta Edad Media anterior al año 1137", in *Anuario de Estudios Medievales*, 21, 1991, pp. 471-492.

³³ C. García Turza and J. García Turza (coord.), *Los manuscritos visigóticos. Estudio paleográfico y codicológico*, vol. 1: *Códices riojanos datados*, Logroño: Fundación San Millán de la Cogolla, 2002, 77-115; M. C. Díaz y Díaz, *Libros y librerías en la Rioja altomedieval*, Logroño: Diputación Provincial. Servicio de Cultura, 1979.

³⁴ M. Herrero de la Fuente and J. A. Fernández Flórez, "Sobre la escritura visigótica en León y Castilla durante su etapa primitiva (ss. VII-X): algunas reflexiones," in J. Alturo Perucho, M. Torras Cortina and A. Castro Correa (coords. and eds.), *La escritura visigótica en la Península Ibérica: nuevas aportaciones*, Bellaterra: Servei de Publicacions de la Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 2012, pp. 55-104.

³⁵ A. Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica en Galicia. I. Diócesis de Lugo" (PhD diss.), Bellaterra: Servei de Publicacions de la Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 2012, p. 324.

preference for more traditional features,³⁶ likewise observed in codicological practices.³⁷ All these sub-types within geographical variants share the main graphic characteristics, but also present certain minor traits that point to a more precise location. The Castilian and Leonese hands differ as a consequence of the cultural prominence of the monastic centres of the former, seen in a more graceful and slender script in Castile than in Leon, although this may be a generalisation that requires further study.³⁸ Galician sources display the graphic characteristics to be expected in that area, but later than usual due to the slower adoption of new graphic trends in this remote region.³⁹

A further level of classification has been determined yet within each of these regional variants given the specific graphic practices of scribes working under the same roof, trained in the same production centre and originating from the same school.

The degree of detail achieved in analysing sources produced in a particular centre has enabled specialists to differentiate certain traits that tend to, or are more likely to, correspond to scribes trained in or related to a particular production centre. As an example, within the Galician regional variant, in which territory it can be said that a consistent Astur-Leonese Visigothic script was employed, the graphic model differs slightly depending on the production centre under study, in both its graphic characteristics and its evolution. It has been demonstrated that the Visigothic script used in or nearby the diocesan city of Lugo is different from that used in the episcopal, later archiepiscopal, see of Santiago de Compostela, the former being closer to a traditional style while the latter is more open to graphic change (earlier adoption of Caroline minuscule features) and innovation (heavily mixing the minuscule and cursive typological variants). In analysing the graphic evidence from those two centres, therefore, the cultural – particularly merging the political and the social – context is instrumental as it influenced the graphic adaptation of the script to a more dynamic environment where, in the case of Santiago de Compostela, a larger number of scribes, trained in a prime school, were developing their careers.⁴⁰ In these poles of attraction, the major schools and production centres, the main ecclesiastical institutions of each regional area, the script used was different.

Even going further in the degree of localisation of sources by the graphic characteristics of the script, a consequence of the distinction of main scribes and prominent cultural centres is the parallel differentiation of scribes who were not trained in centres of the first order, whose script was a more modest representation of the Visigothic graphic model. Graphically speaking, the calligraphic expertise of those scribes peripheral to a main centre (see the example in Figure 5) easily individualises them within the broad context of Visigothic script sources – those hands skilled enough to replicate a graphic model but not enough to be commissioned with the copying of the main manuscripts of the time, royal charters or codices, for example. Moreover, it is not

³⁶ A. M. Mundó i Marcet, "La datación de los códices litúrgicos visigóticos toledanos", in *Hispania Sacra*, XVIII/35, 1965, pp. 1-25; A. Millares Carlo, *Los códices visigóticos de la catedral toledana. Cuestiones cronológicas y de procedencia* (Discurso en la Real Academia de la Historia), Madrid: Real Academia de la Historia, 1935.

³⁷ E. E. Rodríguez Díaz, "Los manuscritos mozárabes: una encrucijada de culturas", in M. Maser and K. Herbers (coord.), *Die Mozaraber. Perspektiven und Definitionem der Forschung*, München: LIT Verlag, 2011, pp. 75-103.

³⁸ J. A. Fernández Flórez, "Un calígrafo-miniaturista del año mil. Vigila de Albelda", in *Codex aquilarensis: Cuadernos de investigación del Monasterio de Santa María la Real*, 16, 2000, pp. 153-180 (166-167, 178).

³⁹ A. Castro Correa, "The regional study of Visigothic script: Visigothic script vs. Caroline minuscule in Galicia", in Eef A. Overgaauw and Martin Schubert (dir.), "*Change*" in *medieval and Renaissance scripts and manuscripts: proceedings of the 19th Colloquium of the Comité international de paléographie latine (Berlin, September 16-18, 2015)*, Turnhout: Brepols, 2019, pp. 25-35.

⁴⁰ On Galician Visigothic script, see A. Castro Correa, "Visigothic script vs. Caroline minuscule: the collision of two cultural worlds in twelfth-century Galicia", in *Mediaeval Studies*, 78, 2016, pp. 203-242.

merely a matter of these scribes producing a rougher or less calligraphic-looking script that results in codices with a less careful general appearance, but rather that their way of graphically depicting the perfect graphic model they had on their minds does not demonstrate the ease achieved with continuous and dedicated practice, which they would possibly achieve if they had time, will, and a centre behind with a clear economic stability that could afford to maintain its activity. In studying these scribes, the identification of secondary monasteries and parishes through references to topography is crucial since reconstructing such less-studied milieu helps to reconstruct the similarly less well-known daily life of medieval people and to study their relationship with the written world. These secondary monastic and parochial schools played a fundamental role in the education of monks and of the people living outside the main medieval post-Roman *villae* as well as in the development of written production by expanding writing to all social classes.⁴¹

3.2. The script and its time

The study of Visigothic script sources to date has rendered significant results allowing the differentiation of geographical, regional and even local variants of the script and simultaneously determining a methodology for the study of their cultural context. Moreover, while classifying the sources by these criteria, relevant considerations regarding the chronology and evolution of the script have become evident. Before Muñoz y Rivero and Lowe, already in the late eighteenth century, Merino de Jesucristo noted that the general aspect of Visigothic script changed around the tenth century.⁴² That century is still considered a turning point in the historical evolution of the script by modern scholarship.

In classifying the written evidence preserved into geographical groups, it progressively became evident to what extent Visigothic script was used in peninsular and southern French soil, filling the graphical gap between the scripts of the late Roman Empire and the supranational medieval script which would come to replace them, Caroline minuscule (see Table 2).

Besides advances regarding the genetic origins of the script (the script(s) Visigothic comes from),⁴³ its chronological and geographical origins have been discussed considering the extant sources preserved, their chronology and assumed place of origin. The attribution of a specific geographical origin to Visigothic script is a question that remains open given the lack of written examples from the script's earlier period to allow a better cultural contextualisation. Some scholars have proposed the Catalan and Septimanian areas considering the supposed origins of the earliest extant codices; others suggest Toledo or Seville due to their cultural prominence.⁴⁴ Establishing a date from which it can be said Visigothic script was already formed, or at least showed its fundamental traits, entailed further analysis of the post-Roman and pre-Visigothic

⁴¹ J. Alturo Perucho, "El sistema educativo en la Cataluña altomedieval", in *Memoria ecclesiae*, XII, 1997, pp. 31-60 and J. Alturo Perucho, *El llibre manuscrit a Catalunya. Orígens i esplendor*, Barcelona: Generalitat de Catalunya, 2001 (1^a ed.), pp. 47-127.

⁴² A. Merino de Jesucristo, *Escuela Paleographica, ó de leer letras antiguas, desde la entrada de los godos en España, hasta nuestros tiempos*, Madrid: por D. Juan Antonio Lozano, impresor de S.M., 1780, p. 74.

⁴³ On the genetic origins of Visigothic script (or of the Visigothic scripts, plural, since different genetic origins have been determined for the two main typological variants of the script, cursive and minuscule), see M^a del C. del Camino Martínez, "Los orígenes de la escritura visigótica: ¿Otras posibilidades para su estudio?", in M. C. Díaz y Díaz (coord.), *Actas del VIII Coloquio del Comité Internacional de Paleografía Latina (Madrid-Toledo, 29 septiembre-1 octubre 1987)*, Madrid: Joyas Bibliográficas (Serie Estudios y Ensayos 16), 1990, pp. 29-38.

⁴⁴ On this debate, see J. Alturo Perucho, "La escritura visigótica. Estado de la cuestión", in *Archiv für Diplomatik*, 50, 2004, pp. 347-386 (365).

scripts – that preserved in the Visigothic slate tablets,⁴⁵ in some few inscriptions⁴⁶ and in the five extant charters of the Visigothic (Visigothic kingdom) chancery,⁴⁷ as well as in the supposedly oldest codices with text already written or copied in Visigothic script dated to the mid-seventh and early eighth centuries.⁴⁸ The analysis of all these sources has provided scholars with a more precise knowledge of how, graphically speaking, Visigothic script came into being and what might have been its initial chronology, generally agreeing to place in around the late sixth or early seventh century.⁴⁹ From this date to the first examples of proper Visigothic script preserved, the script went through a process of configuration of its basic graphic model, which would be replicated, adapting and evolving, through its use (see Figure 3).

Periodisation of Visigothic minuscule script	
Septimania	second half of the 7 th c. to circa 900
Catalonia	second half of the 7 th c. to 900
Mozarabic	late 8 th c. to mid-11 th c.
Castile	early 9 th c. to mid-12 th c.
Leon	early 9 th c. to mid-12 th c.
Toledo	early 9 th c. to circa 1300
Portugal	late 9 th c. to late 12 th c.
Galicia	early 10 th c. to late 12 th /early 13 th c.

Table 2. Approximate chronology of Visigothic minuscule script according to the latest techniques.

a) First stage: 'experimental' or 'incipient'

Given the manuscript and epigraphic evidence preserved and the periodisation of the script, the study of Visigothic script's evolution over the centuries began by considering its earliest known examples.

The graphic characteristics shown in the oldest Visigothic script manuscripts, adding those considerations coming from the formation phase of Visigothic script well attested in the slate tablets, encouraged scholars to define a first stage in the evolution of the script, referred to as 'experimental' or 'incipient' and chronologically placed from around the early eighth century to the early tenth. Graphic examples of this early stage show a script that is not yet fully formed. It tends to be wider than it is tall, with short arches for letters such as *m* or *n* and little development of ascenders and descenders (which also tend to display a slight inclination to the left, particularly

⁴⁵ I. Velázquez Soriano, *Documentos de época visigoda escritos en pizarra (siglos VI-VIII)*, Turnhout: Brepols, 2000 and I. Velázquez Soriano, "La escritura visigótica cursiva en su período primitivo", in J. Alturo Perucho, M. Torras Cortina and A. Castro Correa (coords. and eds.), *La escritura visigótica en la Península Ibérica: nuevas aportaciones*, Bellaterra: Servei de Publicacions de la Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 2012, pp. 15-53.

⁴⁶ M. Herrero de la Fuente and J. A. Fernández Flórez, "Sobre la escritura visigótica en León y Castilla durante su etapa primitiva (ss. VII-X): algunas reflexiones", in J. Alturo Perucho, M. Torras Cortina and A. Castro Correa (coords. and eds.), *La escritura visigótica en la Península Ibérica: nuevas aportaciones*, Bellaterra: Servei de Publicacions de la Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 2012, pp. 55-104 (69-81).

⁴⁷ A. M. Mundó i Marcet, "Los diplomas visigodos originales en pergamino. Transcripción y comentario con un regesto de la época visigoda" (PhD diss.), Barcelona: Universitat de Barcelona, 1970 (unpublished).

⁴⁸ See footnote 1 for references.

⁴⁹ J. Alturo Perucho, "La escritura visigótica. Estado de la cuestión", in *Archiv für Diplomatik*, 50, 2004, pp. 347-386 (379-383).

in the oldest examples). The pen stroke is thick, with a consequent excess of ink, mostly prominent in the approach stroke of those tall letters. This initial phase of the script has slightly different characteristics depending on its production centre or school.⁵⁰ Likewise, it varies depending on the typological variant of the script.⁵¹

b) Second stage: 'developed'

The continuous use of the script led to a more calligraphic execution which has led scholars to distinguish a second stage of evolution identified as 'developed', chronologically corresponding to sources from the tenth to the early eleventh century.⁵² To this period belongs the manuscript production carried out in Castilian-Leonese monasteries by scribes such as Florencio of Valeránica⁵³ or Vigila of Albelda⁵⁴ in the mid-tenth century. Their script is taller than it is wide, with thin ascenders and descenders that extend vertically above and below the baseline, and an approach stroke marked by a fine diagonal stroke rising to the right.⁵⁵ In areas such as Catalonia and Septimania, this stage was never achieved since Visigothic script was in use there only until *circa* 900. The script in these areas does show, however, traits of the next stage, since both geographical variants incorporated features of Caroline minuscule into their alphabets and abbreviation systems from the early/mid-ninth century. Examples of Mozarabic Visigothic script from this period are also scarce because of the tendency to preserve archaic features among scribes, whose archaism is explained by their isolation from the coeval graphic evolution of the script in northern Iberia.

c) Third stage: 'transition' or 'decay'

A later stage of graphic evolution, named 'transition' or 'decay', has also been determined by considering the incorporation into Visigothic script hands of graphic elements that correspond to the graphic system of Caroline minuscule, which began to appear in manuscripts around the mid-eleventh century.⁵⁶ This general chronology varies slightly depending on the geographical variant, as has been noted for the eastern areas of the Iberian Peninsula and Septimania. Focusing also on charters rather than only on codices (since they allow a more precise chronology and their script is comparable to what is expected in codices, because the same scribe wrote and copied both types of source many times), the periodisation goes as follows:

In Aragon and Navarre the beginning of a transitional period can be placed in the mid-eleventh century with the last example of Visigothic script dating to 1162; in Castile and Leon the transition

⁵⁰ A. Millares Carlo, *Tratado de Paleografía Española*, 3 vols., Madrid: Editorial Espasa-Calpe, 1983 (2^a ed., con la colaboración de J. M. Ruiz Asencio), vol. I, p. 132.

⁵¹ On the evolution of the cursive variant by periods and geographical areas, see A. Millares Carlo, *Consideraciones sobre la escritura visigótica cursiva*, León: Centro de Estudios e Investigación San Isidoro (Colección Fuentes y estudios de historia leonesa, 8), Archivo Histórico Diocesano, 1973 and A. Millares Carlo, *Tratado de Paleografía Española*, 3 vols., Madrid: Editorial Espasa-Calpe, 1983 (2^a ed., con la colaboración de J. M. Ruiz Asencio), vol. I, pp. 83-87. On both, see A. M. Mundó i Marcet, "Notas para la historia de la escritura visigótica en su período primitivo", in *Bivium: Homenaje a Manuel Cecilio Díaz y Díaz*, Madrid: Gredos, 1983, pp. 175-196 (182-196).

⁵² For notes on geographical graphic dissimilarities, see A. Millares Carlo, *Tratado de Paleografía Española*, 3 vols., Madrid: Editorial Espasa-Calpe, 1983 (2^a ed., con la colaboración de J. M. Ruiz Asencio), vol. I, p. 135.

⁵³ J. Escalona Monge, I. Velázquez Soriano and P. Juárez Benítez, "Identification of the sole extant original charter issued by Fernán González, Count of Castile (932-970)", in *Journal of Medieval Iberian Studies*, 4/2, 2012, pp. 259-288.

⁵⁴ J. A. Fernández Flórez, "Un calígrafo-miniaturista del año mil. Vigila de Albelda", in *Codex aquilarensis: Cuadernos de investigación del Monasterio de Santa María la Real*, 16, 2000, pp. 153-180 (177).

⁵⁵ A. Millares Carlo, *Tratado de Paleografía Española*, 3 vols., Madrid: Editorial Espasa-Calpe, 1983 (2^a ed., con la colaboración de J. M. Ruiz Asencio), vol. I, pp. 136-138.

⁵⁶ A. Millares Carlo, *Tratado de Paleografía Española*, 3 vols., Madrid: Editorial Espasa-Calpe, 1983 (2^a ed., con la colaboración de J. M. Ruiz Asencio), vol. I, pp. 139-143.

started in the late eleventh century and the last example dates from 1135; in Cantabria and Asturias the influence of Caroline minuscule was attested from the end of the eleventh century and the most recent examples of Visigothic script are dated to 1136 and 1166; in Portugal, like Aragon, the influence was clear in the mid-eleventh century, and the last Visigothic script charter dates from 1172; while in Galicia, even though Caroline influence was present from the late eleventh century, Visigothic script was used until 1199 (1234 in rural areas).⁵⁷

Signs of this Caroline minuscule influence include the addition to the Visigothic alphabet of some Caroline minuscule letters (significantly *a*, *g*, *t* and tall *s*, profuse use of square *r* and a lack of tall *l*), ligatures (tall ligature *c+t* and *s+t*), and abbreviations (macron without dot; semicircle or semicolon for the endings *-us* and *-ue*; abbreviation of *-er* on *h*, *t* and *u*, *-ur* on *t*, *-en* on *m*, *-er* on *u*, *-unt* on *r*; increased use of Tironian signs and *notae iuris*; abbreviation by superscript letter; and specific forms like those of *autem*, *quoniam*, *nobis/uobis* and *noster/uester*, among others) besides the adoption of a generally more rounded, less slender aspect to the script. As noted, this last stage in the script's evolution is present in northern and north-western geographical variants alike, slightly more developed in Galician sources since the script was in use longer there than in any other area except for Toledo.

4. Conclusions

Dating and placing a written sample correctly in context, in Visigothic script or any other medieval script for that matter, is one of the most difficult tasks and the foundation of continued study of the source. It entails the consideration of many variables together, as noted in the paragraphs above, but also the awareness of all those many other disciplines that come into play too: epigraphy for the study of the oldest preserved examples and of medieval inscriptions; codicology and diplomatics to analyse the structure of books and charters, which changes by area and period; philology to interpret the change in language with the progressive development of Romance and to use the information this provides about where and when a source most likely belongs; art history to dig into the aesthetic information that illumination programmes offer on routes of cultural exchange; textual analysis to place the texts in context; history to put all this information together and reconstruct a cultural environment for the script to live in. Only by making the most of all the information a manuscript source provides can its context be reconstructed.

The methodology employed in the study of Visigothic script determines that the first step should be the elaboration of a complete graphic profile of the hand which represents the graphic model in use. This profile should be as complete as possible, including a full analysis of the uppercase and lowercase alphabets the scribe used, of the ligatures and nexuses that sometimes deviate from the standard in a very personal manner, and of the abbreviation signs and abbreviations.⁵⁸ Once the researcher has this profile, the dating and placing exercise can begin, and it is ruled by a simple, but not easy, procedure: comparison.⁵⁹ The only way to place a manuscript sample

⁵⁷ With notes on cultural context, see A. Castro Correa, "Visigothic script vs. Caroline minuscule: the collision of two cultural worlds in twelfth-century Galicia", in *Mediaeval Studies*, 78, 2016, pp. 203-242 and A. Castro Correa, "Leaving the past behind, adapting to the future: transitional and polygraphic Visigothic-Caroline minuscule scribes", in *CSIC Anuario de Estudios Medievales*, 50/1, 2020 (in press).

⁵⁸ For a full list of features to consider in the palaeographical analysis of a Visigothic script hand, see A. Castro Correa, "Palaeography, computer-aided palaeography and digital palaeography. Digital tools applied to the study of Visigothic script," in T. L. Andrews and C. Macé (eds.), *Analysis of Ancient and Medieval Texts and Manuscripts: Digital Approaches*, Turnhout: Brepols, 2014, pp. 247-272.

⁵⁹ A. M. Mundó i Marcet, "Méthode comparative-statistique pour la datation des manuscrits non datés," in G. Silagi (ed.), *Paläographie 1981. Colloquium des Comité International de Paléographie (15-18 September*

without a date or stated place of origin in its context with some certainty is to find similarities between its hand(s) and those of other coeval sources that can be placed and dated with confidence on the information they provide.⁶⁰ The systematic comparison of one source with, potentially, many others exponentially increases the amount of time devoted to conducting research and the notes derived from that work, demanding from the specialist not only the careful consideration of many aspects and a significant appreciation for detail, but the ability to retain all that information. As the corpus of sources increases, this task becomes progressively more complex.

The incorporation of digital tools into the palaeographical analysis of written evidence, which began not so long ago, has been seen as a way to ease the task described. Although much of the work to be done still lies in manual analysis, the addition to the worktable of software to digitally alter images has increased in parallel to the availability of digital surrogates of manuscripts. From that starting point, the options have proliferated significantly, surpassing the mere intention of replicating a manual analysis to retrieve text that is hidden to the naked eye, to allow the analysis of the chemical composition and the order of deposition of inks on the written surface or to provide automatic segmentation of graphic features and transcriptions of the text the sources contain.⁶¹ This process of assimilating digital tools to conduct traditional palaeographic analysis or to open up new research questions based on manuscript sources is widespread in all fields of palaeographical studies, and is starting to infiltrate the study of Visigothic script. In 2011 an open access website was launched: *DigiPal: Digital Resource and Database of Manuscripts, Palaeography and Diplomatic* (<http://www.digipal.eu>; in a new version: Archetype <http://archetype.ink/>). Developed by a multidisciplinary team of specialists as a tool to ease the annotation, description, exploration and communication of graphic evidence through complex mark-up structures, *DigiPal* is intended to help build graphic profiles of scribes while providing the option to search within those files with an exceptional degree of detail while sharing research. Due to its flexibility to adapt to the specific characteristics of the corpus under study, the software is being applied to many different groups of sources and, since 2015, has been tested to help contextualise Visigothic script manuscripts (*VisigothicPal: Dating and placing Visigothic script*: www.visigothicpal.com). The incorporation of *DigiPal* into the study of Visigothic script manuscript sources provides a new approach. It is intended to progressively gather the fundamental information on the script compiled through the steps briefly alluded to in this article

1981), München: Arbo-Gesellschaft (Series Münchener Beiträge zur Mediävistik und Renaissance-Forschung, 32), 1982, pp. 53-58.

⁶⁰ Although it is frequently advised to compare one source with other possible coeval ones, merging hands working on codices and on charters, it should be noted that the type of script a scribe chose to use tended to correspond with the manuscript type he was producing. Scribes such as Florencio of Valeránica or Vigila of Albelda copied codices in Visigothic minuscule script but wrote charters in Visigothic cursive script. Likewise, some scribes used different hands depending to the grantor or recipient of the document they were commissioned to write, making it difficult to identify them as material authors of the charters (see A. Castro Correa, "Palaeography, computer-aided palaeography and digital palaeography. Digital tools applied to the study of Visigothic script", in T. L. Andrews and C. Macé (eds.), *Analysis of Ancient and Medieval Texts and Manuscripts: Digital Approaches*, Turnhout: Brepols, 2014, pp. 247-272 (265, Fig. 6); also A. Castro Correa, "Leaving the past behind, adapting to the future: transitional and polygraphic Visigothic-Caroline minuscule scribes", in *CSIC Anuario de Estudios Medievales*, 50/1, 2020 (in press), on polygraphic scribes). Therefore, although some scribes could use the same hand regardless of the type of source or display distinctive features of style that could individualise them even when using different typological variants of the script, the comparison of graphic samples of different kinds should be conducted with caution.

⁶¹ On computer aided palaeography and digital palaeography, albeit a bit outdated, is still of use A. Castro Correa, "Palaeography, computer-aided palaeography and digital palaeography. Digital tools applied to the study of Visigothic script", in T. L. Andrews and C. Macé (eds.), *Analysis of Ancient and Medieval Texts and Manuscripts: Digital Approaches*, Turnhout: Brepols, 2014, pp. 247-272.

while providing an open discussion board to promote Visigothic script studies and solve the many remaining research questions awaiting answers.

The analysis of a given Visigothic minuscule script hand, according to the variables briefly summarised in this essay, can prove useful but it still offers guidance only. At this point, a detailed and illustrated (digitally or not) catalogue of dated and datable manuscripts in Visigothic script is needed to better ascertain the contextualisation of manuscript material that does not provide historical information.

5. Epilogue: hints and tips

As stated in the abstract of this essay, the notes above are a brief summary of the current state of the art of research on the Visigothic minuscule script used in codices, intended to provide scholars with some hints when dealing with its contextualisation – at least enough to critically approach published references and know which one(s) are best suited to help with the study of a specific source. As a way of testing this quick guide, below are some examples of the application of Lowe's rules together with further notes on specific problems yet to be solved by scholarship that, likewise, help to highlight that the present article is a summary and not a comprehensive review.

a) Example 1 (Figure 6)

The script is elegant, with thin ascenders and descenders, and there is differentiation of the two forms of the syllable *ti*. Therefore, according to Lowe's rules, this hand most likely dates to the eleventh or twelfth century. The scribe who copied this text was aligned with the northern school of Visigothic minuscule script (Astur-leonese) for it does not show significant elements proper of the Mozarabic geographical variant. Given that the hand shows influence of the Caroline minuscule system (for example, in the form of *nobis*, *quod*, *-us* and *per*), although not profusely, it belongs to the last stage of the script's development. All this considered, this hand/scribe could be dated with some certainty to the late eleventh century. Current scholarship⁶² proposes that it was indeed copied in Silos (Burgos) around 1080. So, this manuscript is an example of an Astur-Leonese (Castilian) transitional Visigothic minuscule script.

b) Example 2 (Figure 7)

In this example, the script shows characteristic thick strokes, the ends of the ascenders are clubbed, and those of the nasals continue to the right side on the base line. There is little distinction of the two forms of *ti*. The hand, like example 1, corresponds to the graphic model used in northern schools for it shows no Mozarabic influence. Besides, current scholarship considers, although it is not always true, that written samples from Castile tend to be more calligraphic (see previous example) than those from Leon. Therefore, this text was most likely copied in Leonese territory around the tenth century, and indeed it has a colophon that dates it as copied in 902.⁶³

⁶² On this manuscript, see A. Castro Correa, "The scribes of the Silos Apocalypse (British Library Add. ms. 11695) and the *scriptorium* of Silos in the late eleventh century", in *Speculum*, 95/2, 2020 (in press); A. Millares Carlo, *Corpus de códices visigóticos*, 2 vols., Las Palmas de Gran Canaria: Gobierno de Canarias; Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia, Centro Asociado de Las Palmas, 1999, p. 169, n° 264; M. C. Díaz y Díaz, *Códices visigóticos en la monarquía leonesa*, León: Centro de Estudios e Investigación "San Isidoro" (C.S.I.C.), 1983, pp. 347-348, 457-459.

Available at <http://archivesetmanuscrits.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/cc70405r/ca19816548>.

⁶³ On this manuscript, see A. Millares Carlo, *Corpus de códices visigóticos*, 2 vols., Las Palmas de Gran Canaria: Gobierno de Canarias; Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia, Centro Asociado de Las Palmas, 1999, pp. 114-115, n° 164; M. C. Díaz y Díaz, *Códices visigóticos en la monarquía leonesa*, León: Centro de Estudios e Investigación "San Isidoro" (C.S.I.C.), 1983, pp. 117-148.

Available at <http://bdh.bne.es/bnearch/detalle/bdh0000043777>.

This manuscript is an example of an Astur-Leonese (Leonese) developed Visigothic minuscule script.

c) Example 3 (Figure 9)

This is a clear example of Mozarabic Visigothic script: see the characteristic form of the letter *t*, similar to an infinity sign, and the open *e*. Geographically speaking, then, either the codex was copied in southern Iberia, in a Mozarabic centre, or the scribe was trained in a Mozarabic centre and had travelled to another – this codex could have been copied anywhere. Dating manuscripts written in this variant is also difficult because it has yet to be determined how the script evolved given Mozarabic scribes' tendency to preserve traditional (older) features. As a result, this codex has been dated as to the ninth, tenth, eleventh, twelfth or thirteenth century depending on the scholar and sometimes even on the publication.⁶⁴ Given the current state of the art, it is almost impossible to date a Mozarabic example with some certainty only by looking at the script; however, and luckily, it is easy to recognise it.

⁶⁴ On this manuscript, see A. Millares Carlo, *Corpus de códices visigóticos*, 2 vols., Las Palmas de Gran Canaria: Gobierno de Canarias; Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia, Centro Asociado de Las Palmas, 1999, pp. 193-194, nº 323.

Figure 1. Detail of Visigothic minuscule script. The 'Silos Apocalypse' © British Library Board, Add. ms. 11695, f. 8r.

Figure 2. Overview of the same hand's minuscule alphabet, ligatures and nexuses (left), and abbreviation system (right).

Figure 3. From top to bottom: © Madrid, Real Academia de la Historia, Cód. 34, f. 21r (9th c.), © Madrid, Archivo Histórico Nacional, cód. 1097B, f. 25r (late 10th c.), © British Library Board, Add. ms. 11695, f. 8r (late 11th c.).

Figure 4. From top to bottom, representative examples of: Mozarabic Visigothic script (© Madrid, Biblioteca Nacional, Vitr. 14-3, f. 2v (9th c.)),⁶⁵ Riojan Visigothic script (© Madrid, Real Academia de la Historia, Cód. 34, f. 21r (9th c.)),⁶⁶ Septimanian Visigothic script (© Lyon, Bibl. Municipale, MS0443, f. 7r (early 9th c.)).⁶⁷

Figure 5. Example of Visigothic minuscule script classified by current scholarship as 'rural' © Madrid, Biblioteca Nacional, MSS/10092, f. 1v (9th c.; Mozarabic)⁶⁸

Figure 6. © Paris, Bibliothèque Nationale, nouv. acq. lat. 2176, f. 359v.

Figure 7. © Madrid, Biblioteca Nacional, MSS/10007, f. 82.

Figure 8. © Toledo, Archivo y Biblioteca Capitular, 35.5, f. 201v.

Abstract:

This essay summarises the current state of the art regarding the dating and placing of codices copied in Visigothic minuscule script, one of the two basic typological variants of the main graphic system used in the Iberian Peninsula during the Middle Ages (8th to 13th century). As a brief overview of the palaeographical method designed to graphically contextualise these sources, this work is intended to be a quick guide for Manuscript Studies scholars who are not specialists on the topic but nevertheless work with Visigothic script material in their research, as well as for readers interested in knowing more about medieval written sources. The pages that follow are also intended to stimulate debate on Visigothic script, the study of its variants, evolution and contextualisation, likewise introducing a new software build to help with the detailed analysis of the extant manuscript material.

Keywords:

⁶⁵ On this manuscript, see A. Millares Carlo, *Corpus de códices visigóticos*, 2 vols., Las Palmas de Gran Canaria: Gobierno de Canarias; Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia, Centro Asociado de Las Palmas, 1999, pp. 121-122, n^o 173.

Available at <http://bdh.bne.es/bnearch/detalle/bdh0000051810>.

⁶⁶ On this manuscript, see A. Millares Carlo, *Corpus de códices visigóticos*, 2 vols., Las Palmas de Gran Canaria: Gobierno de Canarias; Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia, Centro Asociado de Las Palmas, 1999, p. 131, n^o 193.

Available at <http://bibliotecadigital.rah.es/dgbrah/es/consulta/registro.cmd?id=41>.

⁶⁷ On this manuscript, see A. Millares Carlo, *Corpus de códices visigóticos*, 2 vols., Las Palmas de Gran Canaria: Gobierno de Canarias; Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia, Centro Asociado de Las Palmas, 1999, p. 90, n^o 122.

Available at <http://numelyo.bm-lyon.fr/manuscrits/list.php?recherche=Orig%C3%A8ne&mode=auteur>.

⁶⁸ On this manuscript, see A. Millares Carlo, *Corpus de códices visigóticos*, 2 vols., Las Palmas de Gran Canaria: Gobierno de Canarias; Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia, Centro Asociado de Las Palmas, 1999, vol. I, pp. 120-121, n^o 171.

Available at <http://bdh.bne.es/bnearch/detalle/bdh0000060234>.

Palaeography, Visigothic script, Medieval Manuscripts, Codices

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